

Note

This document includes two interview protocols which formed the basis of a semi-structured interview study. The first protocol was used for conversations with individuals who self-identified as having reused research data, and the second was used to guide discussions with individuals who do not reuse data.

Meaningful Data Counts Interview Protocol (Re-users)

Introduction

- Thank you for participating in this study and for your time today.
- Have you received and completed the Informed consent form?
- Do you have any questions about the informed consent form?
- With your permission this interview will be recorded. If you consent, I will begin recording now.

- Goals of project and study
 - As you read in the informed consent, this study is part of the Meaningful Data Counts Project, which investigates how researchers across disciplines reuse and cite data and how data work can be rewarded in academia.

 - As part of this project, we conducted a survey, which you completed earlier this year. You indicated that you would be willing to participate in future research, which is why we contacted you.

 - The goal of this interview is to learn more about your practices of working with, reusing, and citing data, as well as your preferences for how you think your own research data work could be rewarded and recognized. We will ask questions, e.g., about how you work with and use data, as well as your citation and referencing practices for both data and academic literature.

- Overview of interview
 - We will begin with some questions about demographics and your research in general to provide context for your answers.
 - The majority of the interview will be conversation centered around a publication, preprint or manuscript which you selected in advance of the interview, which is an example of a case/project where you used data which you did not create/collect yourself.

Part 1: Demographics / Background

1. What is your professional role / title?
2. How long have you been working in this capacity? In the profession overall?

3. In what discipline would you situate your current research?
4. Could you describe your research in 2-3 sentences to provide a bit of context to the conversation?

Part 2: Researchers' practices: Sample publication

Let's start with a short definition of some terms:

- **Data:** We broadly define data as entities used as evidence of phenomena for the purposes of research or scholarship. Examples of data range from observations in spreadsheets to literature corpora to physical samples to interview transcripts.

5. Which data do you normally work with?

Definitions continued

- We are going to be talking about "data reuse" and "data sharing". These are terms which we use a lot, but which I realize may be unfamiliar to you.
- **Data reuse** means using data that has been created by another person, organization, etc. for any purpose.
- **Data sharing:** There are different interpretations of this term, but it broadly means sharing data that you have created or collected. In our research, data sharing is typically thought to be done via an infrastructure, database, or data repository, but we also know that data sharing happens more informally, person-to-person.

6. Before the interview, you selected a publication which you would like to discuss. Let's look at this publication together. Could you tell me a bit about the study, i.e. the aim of the research, or the methods used?
7. Looking at this study, which data did you (and/or your co-authors) create? Which did you "reuse", i.e. data which you did not create?

Prompts/Key Ideas:

- Why did you choose this data instead of other data?
 - Was there any data used for this project that did not make it into this publication?
8. How much of your work is "data work"? Data work is defined broadly - think of collecting data but also managing data, documenting data, cleaning data, etc.

9. Do you ever reuse data for any other purposes, besides what we talked about in this example? How frequently?
10. Returning to the publication you brought, did you cite, reference or otherwise mention the data which you used in this publication?

IF YES: Could you show me the citation/reference in the publication?

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- What did you cite? (i.e. a particular dataset, a data repository, an article)
 - How did you cite it? (i.e. with a in-text mention, a footnote, a formal citation)
 - Using more than one strategy or a combination of strategies?
 - Why did you cite or mention data in this instance?
 - Any other reasons? (i.e., to credit data creators, to help make data findable, to correct or criticize data)
 - Would you say this is typical of your citation practice?
 - Did you encounter any challenges in citing data in this instance or in other cases?
 - Did any of the reviewers/editors ask you about the data or to cite it?
 - We realize that there are some uses which may not make it into a publication. But were there any data which you used but which you did not cite, mention or reference?
11. In general, how do you decide when to cite or mention data and when not to? What is “worth” another type of mention or reference? What is in a reference list or not?
 - Is the “cost” (time, effort) of reusing data different from using literature?
 - Do you consider a citation to a related article to be a data citation?
 12. Would you say that referencing/citing data is common in your discipline or research community?

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- Are there supporting infrastructures for data reuse and data citation (e.g., repositories, citation styles)?

We are now going to shift to talking about your preferences for the sharing and reuse of your own data.

Part 3: Preferences for your data

13. Do you share your own data?

IF YES: Can you give an example of how you have shared your data?

Prompts/ Key Ideas:

- What motivates you to share data (i.e. norms, funder requirements, philosophical)?
- If they share in a repository: Do you “co-author” shared data? That is, when you upload data to a repository do you list multiple people as a data creator or just one person? Is that the case even if multiple people were involved in a project?
- When in the research process do you share your data? (i.e., after data collection and cleaning, at time of submission, at time of publication, later)
- Could you speak more about the work involved in sharing your data?
 - How much time does it take to prepare your data?
 - Who does this work?
 - Do you have to give up other tasks in order to spend time working on data sharing and management?
 - Are there any barriers? (i.e., sharing with open licenses, access restrictions, privacy issues)

IF NO: Why not? (i.e., not common, fear of being scooped, too much work)

14. Do you want other people to reuse your data?

IF YES:

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- Why?
- What do they need to do that?

IF NO: Why not?

15. If others reuse your data, how should they acknowledge that use in the publication? (i.e., citing dataset in a reference list, citing paper, mention in text or acknowledgement)

16. Are you interested in tracking whether your data were reused by others?

IF YES:

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- Are you already tracking reuse?
- What do you want to know about your data if they are reused? What information are you interested in? (“What do you want to track? What do you want to know?”)

We would now like to ask what your opinions are on how data are recognized in the context of academic evaluation and assessment.

Part 4: Recognizing & Rewarding / Metrics for reuse

17. How is your research evaluated in the context of your academic career?

Prompts / Key Ideas

- What role do citations and publications in general play in how your research is evaluated?
 - Do you see a citation as a “reward” in any way?
 - Do you think that your publications receive more citations if the data are shared? Is this a motivating factor for you in any way?
- Do data count as the same type of output as, e.g., an article? (Do data count as much to you as another type of research output, e.g., an article? What about to those who are evaluating you or to your peers?)

18. Do you think that data work should be evaluated and/or rewarded? (i.e., data collection and cleaning, data management, data sharing, good workflows, training other researchers)

IF YES: How?

IF NO: Why not?

19. Do you think that data metrics that take into account downloads or citations could help to reward data work?

IF YES: How?

- What else could help to reward or recognize data work?

IF NO: Why not?

- What could help to reward or recognize data work?

Closing

- Final question: In your opinion, where do you see data sharing, reuse, or data citation going in your field and/or research community in the next 5-10 years?
- Do you have any further questions or anything which you would like to add?
- Thank you very much for your time and insight.

Meaningful Data Counts Interview Protocol (Non-reusers)

Introduction

- Thank you for participating in this study and for your time today.
- Have you received and completed the Informed consent form?
- Do you have any questions about the informed consent form?
- With your permission this interview will be recorded. If you consent, I will begin recording now.

- Goals of project and study
 - As you read in the informed consent, this study is part of the Meaningful Data Counts Project, which investigates how researchers across disciplines use, reuse, and cite data and how data work can be rewarded in academia.

 - As part of this project, we conducted a survey, which you completed earlier this year. You indicated that you would be willing to participate in future research, which is why we contacted you.

 - The goal of this interview is to learn more about your practices of working with (and maybe citing or referencing) data, as well as your preferences for how you think your own research data work could be rewarded and recognized.

- Overview of interview
 - We will begin with some questions about demographics and your research in general to provide context for your answers.

 - The majority of the interview will be conversation centered around a publication, preprint, or manuscript which you selected in advance of the interview, which is an example of a case/project which is typical of how you use data in your work.

Part 1: Demographics / Background

1. What is your professional role / title?
2. How long have you been working in this capacity? In the profession overall?
3. In what discipline would you situate your current research?
4. Could you describe your research in 2-3 sentences to provide a bit of context to the conversation?

Part 2: Researchers' practices: Sample publication

Let's start with a short definition of some terms:

- **Data:** We broadly define data as entities used as evidence of phenomena for the purposes of research or scholarship. Examples of data range from observations in spreadsheets to literature corpora to physical samples to interview transcripts.

5. Which data do you normally work with?

Definitions continued

- We are going to be talking about “data reuse” and “data sharing”. These are terms which we use a lot, but which I realize may be unfamiliar to you.
- **Data reuse** means using data that has been created by another person, organization, etc. for any purpose.
- **Data sharing:** There are different interpretations of this term, but it broadly means sharing data that you have created or collected. In our research, data sharing is typically thought to be done via an infrastructure, database, or data repository, but we also know that data sharing happens more informally, person-to-person.

6. Before the interview, you selected a publication which you would like to discuss. Let’s look at this publication together. Could you tell me a bit about the study, i.e., the aim of the research, or the methods used?
7. Looking at this study, could you tell me more about which data were used in this work?

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- How did the data come to be? How were they collected / created /gathered? When?
 - Is this data in this publication a typical example of the type of data you use?
 - Was there any data used for this project that did not make it into this publication?
 - Is citation of data (in reference list or mentioning in the publication) needed in this example?
8. How much of your work is “data work”? Data work is defined broadly - think of collecting data but also managing data, documenting data, cleaning data, etc.
9. You said that you do not reuse data created by others. But have you ever considered doing so?

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- When, why?

10. Could you speak more about your reasons in general for not reusing data?

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- Do you “trust” data created by other people?
- Is it a relevant methodology or common in your community?
- Are there relevant data on your topic?

11. Have you re-used your own data, either in this study or another time? Could you describe that experience more?

12. Would you say that reusing data (that other people create) is common in your discipline or research community?

- Do you think that a study in which data are reused are "worth" as much as a study in which data are created?

13. Are you aware of mandates or policies which encourage the sharing of research data? What about recommendations or policies encouraging the citation of data?

Examples of such policies are those that require that data from federally funded research must be shared, journal policies which require data to be shared, etc.

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- What do you think about these conversations and recommendations? Are they applicable to your work?
- Are there infrastructures (e.g., repositories, persistent identifiers, citation styles) that support data sharing, reuse (and citation)?

14. If data (in your field) are reused in a publication, how do you think they should be acknowledged? (i.e., citing data in a reference list, citing paper, mention in text or acknowledgement)

- Do you consider a citation to a related article to be a data citation?

We are now going to shift to talking about your preferences for the sharing and reuse of your own data.

Part 3: Preferences for your data

15. Do you share your own data?

IF YES: Can you give an example of how you have shared your data?

Prompts/ Key Ideas:

- What motivates you to share data? (i.e., norms, funder requirements, philosophical)
- If they share in a repository: Do you “co-author” shared data? That is, when you upload data to a repository do you list multiple people as a data creator or just one person? Is that the case even if multiple people were involved in a project?
- Do you actually want other people to reuse your data?
- Could you speak more about the work involved in sharing your data?
 - How much time does it take to prepare your data?
 - Who does this work?
 - Do you have to give up other tasks in order to spend time working on data sharing and management?
 - Are there any barriers? (i.e., sharing with open licenses, access restrictions, privacy issues)
 - When in the research process do you share your data? (i.e., after data collection and cleaning, at time of submission, at time of publication, later)

IF NO: Why not? (i.e., not common, fear of being scooped, too much work)

16. If your data are used in a publication, how do you think they should be acknowledged? (i.e., citing data in a reference list, citing paper, mention in text or acknowledgement)
17. If you share data: Are you interested in tracking whether your data were reused by others?

IF YES:

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- Are you already tracking reuse?
- What do you want to know about your data if they are reused? What information are you interested in? (“What do you want to track? What do you want to know?”)

We would now like to ask what your opinions are on how data are recognized in the context of academic evaluation and assessment.

Part 4: Recognizing & Rewarding / Metrics for reuse

18. How is your research evaluated in the context of your academic career?

Prompts / Key Ideas

- What role do citations and publications in general play in how your research is evaluated?
 - Do you see a citation as a “reward” in any way?
 - Do data count as the same type of output as, e.g., an article? (Do data count as much to you as another type of research output, e.g., an article? What about to those who are evaluating you or to your peers?)
 - Do you think that your publications would receive more citations if the data were shared? Is this a motivating factor for you in any way?
19. Do you think that data work should be evaluated and/or rewarded? (i.e., data collection and cleaning, data management, data sharing, good workflows, training other researchers)

IF YES: How?

IF NO: Why not?

20. Do you think that data metrics that take into account downloads or citations could help to reward data work?

IF YES: How?

- What else could help to reward or recognize data work?

IF NO: Why not?

- What could help to reward or recognize data work?

21. As someone who does not reuse data, how would you feel if formal ways for rewarding data sharing or reuse become normal?

Prompts / Key Ideas:

- How would this impact your data practices?
- Would you do anything different?

Closing

- Final question: In your opinion, where do you see data sharing, reuse, or data citation going in your field and/or research community in the next 5-10 years?
- Do you have any further questions or anything which you would like to add?
- Thank you very much for your time and insight.